

Peer Review Journal

ISSN 1817-5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of The Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 2 Number 3 December 2006

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Ali Hassan Al Shimari
Minister of Health

Founding Editor: Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi
Member World Association of Medical Editors

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index Medicus

Copyright Iraqi Ministry of Health

SARS: A new clinical syndrome

Al Mosawi AJ

Abstract

Background: SARS is the first major new infectious disease of this century. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) was first recognized in mid-March 2003 and successfully contained in less than four months. On 5 July 2003, WHO reported that the last human chain of transmission of SARS had been broken? During this period more than 8,000 persons with probable SARS have been diagnosed; 812 patients have died.

SARS is due to an infection with a novel coronavirus which was first identified by researchers in Hong Kong, the United States, and German, termed SARS-associated coronavirus (SARS-CoV). The epidemic of severe atypical pneumonia which was observed in the Chinese province of Guangdong and reported internationally on February 11, 2003, was initially suspected to be linked to a newly emerging influenza virus. The etiologic agent of SARS was identified in late March 2003, when laboratories in Hong Kong, the United States, and Germany found evidence of a novel coronavirus in patients with SARS. This evidence included isolation on cell culture, demonstration by

polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and by micro array test technology, as well as indirect immunofluorescent antibody test. Three weeks later, on April 16, 2003, following a meeting of the collaborating laboratories in Geneva, the WHO announced that this new coronavirus, never before seen in humans or animals, was the cause of SARS. This announcement came after research done by 13 participating laboratories from ten countries had demonstrated that the novel coronavirus met all four of Koch's postulates necessary to prove the causation of disease:

- 1-The pathogen must be found in all cases of the disease.
- 2-It must be isolated from the host and grown in pure culture.
- 3-It must reproduce the original disease when introduced into a susceptible host.
- 4-It must be found in the experimental host so infected.

Proof of the last two requirements was provided after inoculation of cynomolgus macaques (*Macaca fascicularis*) with Vero-cell cultured virus that had previously been isolated from a SARS case. The infection caused interstitial pneumonia resembling SARS, and the virus was isolated from the nose and throat of the monkeys, as shown by polymerase chain reaction with reverse transcription (RT-PCR) and by virus isolation. The isolated virus was

Correspondent author:

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi MD, Ph.D.
Director Postspecialty CME center
Al- Kadhimiya University Hospital.
Baghdad, Iraq

electron microscopy and demonstration of specific genomic sequences by

identical to that inoculated [1]. In April 2003, a Canadian group of researchers from the Michael Smith Genome Sciences Centre in Vancouver, British Columbia, and the National Microbiology Laboratory in Winnipeg, Manitoba, were the first to complete the genome sequencing of the new coronavirus. The genome sequence data of SARS Co-V reveal that the novel agent does not belong to any of the known groups of coronaviruses, including two human coronaviruses, HCoV-OC43 and HCoV-229E, to which it is related. The SARS-CoV genome appears to be equidistant from those of all known coronaviruses.

Morphology: Negative-stain transmission electron microscopy of patient samples and of cell culture supernatants reveals pleomorphic, enveloped coronavirus-like particles with diameters of between 60 and 130 nm. Examination of infected cells by thin-section electron microscopy shows coronavirus-like particles within cytoplasmic membrane-bound vacuoles and the cisternae of the rough endoplasmic reticulum. Extracellular particles accumulate in large clusters, and are frequently seen lining the surface of the plasma membrane [2]. The SARS-CoV genome contains five major open reading frames (ORFs) that encode the replicase polyprotein; the spike (S), envelope (E), and membrane (M) glycoproteins; and the nucleocapsid protein (N). host. The M protein is the major component of the virion envelope. It is the major determinant of virion morphogenesis, selecting S protein for incorporation into virions during viral assembly. There is evidence that suggests that the M protein also selects the genome for incorporation into the virion. One remarkable feature about coronavirus RNA synthesis is the very high rate of RNA-RNA recombination.

Detection: SARS Co-V has been detected in multiple specimens including extracts of lung and kidney tissue by virus isolation or

PCR; bronchoalveolar lavage specimens by virus isolation, electron microscopy and PCR; and sputum or upper respiratory tract swab, aspirate, or wash specimens by PCR [3, 4]. High concentrations of viral RNA of up to 100 million molecules per milliliter were found in sputum [4]. SARS-associated coronavirus RNA was detected in nasopharyngeal aspirates by RT-PCR in 32% at initial presentation (mean 3.2 days after onset of illness) and in 68% at day 14. In stool samples, viral RNA was detected in 97% of patients two weeks after the onset of illness. 42% of urine samples were positive for viral RNA [5]. Viral RNA was also detected at extremely low concentrations in plasma during the acute phase and in feces during the late convalescent phase, suggesting that the virus may be shed in feces for prolonged periods of time [4].

Natural host: At present, no evidence exists to suggest that animal species play a significant role in the epidemiology of SARS outbreaks. Research teams in Hong Kong and Shenzhen detected several coronaviruses that were closely related genetically to the SARS coronavirus in animals taken from a southern Chinese market that was selling wild animals for human consumption. They found the virus in masked palm civets (*Paguma larvata*) as well as some other species. All six of the civets included in the study were found to harbor SARS coronavirus, which was isolated in cell culture or detected by a PCR molecular technique. Serum from these animals also inhibited the growth of SARS coronavirus isolated from humans. Vice versa, human serum from SARS patients inhibited the growth of SARS isolates from these animals. Sequencing of viruses isolated from these animals demonstrated that, with the exception of a small additional sequence, the viruses are identical to the human SARS virus [6, 7].

Transmission of SARS: The SARS coronavirus (SARS Co-V) is predominantly spread in droplets that are shed from the respiratory secretions of infected persons. Fecal or airborne transmission seems to be less frequent. There is growing evidence that a majority of patients might not effectively transmit the virus to other individuals: in Singapore, 162 individuals (81%) of all probable SARS cases had no evidence of transmission of a clinically identifiable illness to other persons [2]. This is in accordance with results from epidemiological studies which indicate that SARS is moderately rather than highly transmissible. In some instances, however, so-called "Superspreaders" patients are able to transmit the SARS virus to a large number of individuals. Superspreaders and nosocomial amplification were the driving factors behind the early 2003 outbreaks.

The fact that the majority of new infections occurred in close contacts of patients, such as household members, healthcare workers, or other patients who were not protected with contact or respiratory precautions, indicates that the virus is predominantly spread by droplets or by direct and indirect contact [2, 8]. The presence of virus in the stool suggests the possibility of oral-fecal transmission [4, 5]. This is reminiscent of characteristics of other coronaviruses [9] and feces are therefore potentially an additional route of transmission. In the Amoy Gardens outbreak, the SARS virus may have been spread through the sewage systems of the buildings.

The airborne spread of SARS does not seem to be a major route of transmission. There are currently no indications that any goods, products or animals arriving from areas with SARS outbreaks pose a risk to public health

Stability and resistance: The virus is stable in feces and urine at room

temperature for at least 1-2 days. The stability seems to be higher in stools from patients with diarrhea (the pH of which is higher than that of normal stool). In supernatants of infected cell cultures, there is only a minimal reduction in the concentration of the virus after 21 days at 4°C and -80°C. After 48 hours at room temperature, the concentration of the virus is reduced by one log only, indicating that the virus is more stable than the other known human coronaviruses under these conditions. However, heating to 56°C inactivates SARS-CoV relatively quickly. Furthermore, the agent loses its infectivity after exposure to different commonly-used disinfectants and fixatives.

Clinical Features

There is no single test that can be used to diagnose SARS with a reasonable degree of accuracy. Diagnosis, therefore, continues to rely on the clinical examination, supported by case definitions that include a travel history. The initial symptoms of SARS are non-specific, complicating the differential diagnosis. Some features of the history, physical examination, radiological and laboratory findings, however, should alert clinicians to the possible diagnosis of SARS, even when the contact history is unreliable. These features are described below. The most common symptom in SARS patients is fever with a body temperature > 38.0°C (100.4°F). Fever is therefore a main criterion in the current WHO case definition for suspected or probable SARS. However, fever may be absent during the early stages of the disease and in individuals with comorbidities who may be impaired in their ability to mount a fever. Fever is mostly associated with other symptoms including chills, rigors, headache, dizziness, malaise, and myalgia [2, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. The frequency of these symptoms within different cohorts is shown in table 1. Thus, the initial

Sputum production, sore throat, coryza, nausea, and vomiting are less common [10, 11]. Inspiratory crackles may be heard at the base of the lung. Wheezing is generally absent. Diarrhea only seemed to be a prominent symptom in the Amoy Gardens' outbreak in Hong Kong [5]. Within the other cohorts published to date, diarrhea was less frequent. The clinical course of SARS is highly variable, ranging from mild symptoms to a severe disease process with respiratory failure and death. Clinical deterioration combined with oxygen desaturation, requiring intensive care and ventilatory support, generally occurs 7 to 10 days after the onset of symptoms [10, 15]. In severe cases, SARS is a fulminate disease, progressing from being "comfortable" to respiratory failure requiring intubation within less than 24 hours [14, 16]. The incubation period of SARS is short. A median incubation period of six days was reported [10, 11]. However, the time from exposure to the onset of symptoms may vary considerably, ranging from 2 to 16 days. The maximum incubation period is probably 10 days [10, 13, 14], followed by the appearance of new lesions. IgG seroconversion, apparently correlating with falls in viral load, could be detected from day 10 to 15. Severe clinical worsening also occurred at this time. Some patients progressed to the third phase, characterized by ARDS necessitating ventilatory support.

Radiographic and hematologic abnormalities

Imaging plays an important role in the diagnosis of SARS and monitoring of response to therapy. A predominant peripheral location, a progression pattern from unilateral focal air-space opacity to

unilateral multifocal or bilateral involvement during treatment, and lack of cavitations, lymphadenopathy, and pleural effusion are the more distinctive radiographic findings [19]. At the onset of fever, 70-80 % of the patients have abnormal chest radiographs [5, 11, 19]. It should be noted that, in a substantial proportion of cases, chest radiographs may be normal during the febrile prodrome, as well as throughout the course of illness. In other cases, radiological evidence of pneumonic changes may precede the fever [20], particularly in individuals with comorbidities who may be impaired in their ability to mount a fever. Chest X-ray findings typically begin with a small, unilateral, patchy shadowing, and progress over 1-2 days to become bilateral and generalized, with interstitial or confluent infiltrates. Air-space opacities eventually develop during the course of the disease. In patients who deteriorate clinically, the air-space opacities may increase in size, extent, and severity [10, 14]. The initial radiographic changes may be indistinguishable from those associated with other causes of bronchopneumonia. The research group from Hong Kong suggested that chest radiographs might offer important diagnostic clues, in particular when, after approximately one week, unilateral, predominantly peripheral areas of consolidation progress to bilateral patchy consolidation, and when the extent of the lung opacities is correlated with the deterioration in respiratory function [10]. There seems to be a predominant involvement of the peripheral-zone. Pleural effusions, cavitations, and hilar lymphadenopathy are usually absent. Respiratory symptoms and positive auscultatory findings are disproportional

mild compared with the chest radiographic findings [10]. One large study focused on radiographic appearances and the pattern of progression [19]. The radiographic appearance of peripheral air-space opacities is indistinguishable from other causes of atypical pneumonia, such as *Mycoplasma*, *Chlamydia*, and *Legionella*, and overlaps with other types of viral pneumonia. The presence of air-space opacity on chest radiographs has been helpful in the confirmation of the diagnosis [19].

During the course of illness, abnormal hematological values are common. Early studies have shown Lymphopenia and thrombocytopenia to be frequent in SARS patients [10, 14, 17, 18]. Progressive Lymphopenia was found in the peripheral blood of 153/157 (98 %) patients with SARS, reaching its lowest point in the second week. Lymphopenia was also shown in hemato-lymphoid organs at postmortem examination. The lymphocyte count commonly recovered in the third week, but about 30% of patients were still Lymphopenia by the fifth week of SARS. Most patients had reduced CD4 and CD8 T cell counts during the early phase of illness, with mean CD4 and CD8 T cell counts of 287 cells/ μ l (normal: 410 to 1590 cells/ μ l) and 242 cells/ μ l (normal: 62 to 559 cells/ μ l), respectively. Low CD4 and CD8 lymphocyte counts at presentation were associated with an adverse outcome in this study [18]. Transient leucopenia was found in 64% of patients during their first week of illness. However, during the second and third week of illness, 61% developed leucocytosis. Neutrophilia ($> 7.500/\mu$ l) developed in 82% of patients, possibly reflecting the wide use of corticosteroids. In total, 55% of patients developed a self-limiting thrombocytopenia, possibly caused by an immune mechanism. With the exception of 2% of patients, the degree of thrombocytopenia was mild (platelet counts

$>50.000/\mu$ l), reaching a low point at the end of the first week. No patient had major bleeding or required platelet transfusion [18].

Virus detection

Polymerase chain Reaction: SARS specific RNA can be detected in various clinical specimens such as blood, stool, respiratory secretions or body tissues by the polymerase chain reaction (PCR)[15,21]. Despite their sometimes high sensitivity, the existing PCR tests cannot rule out, with certainty, the presence of the SARS virus in patients. A valid positive PCR result indicates that there is genetic material (RNA) from the SARS-CoV in the sample. It does not mean, however, that the virus present is infectious, or that it is present in material (RNA) from the SARS-CoV in the sample. It does not mean, however, that the virus present is infectious, or that it is present in a large enough quantity to infect another person. Negative PCR results do not exclude SARS. Besides the possibility of obtaining incorrect, false-negative test results (e.g. through lack of sensitivity), specimen has been collected at a time when the virus may not have present.

Virus isolation: The presence of the infectious virus can be detected by inoculating suitable cell cultures (e.g., Vero cells) with patient specimens (such as respiratory secretions, blood or stool) and propagating the virus in vitro. Once isolated, the virus must be identified as SARS-CoV using further tests. Cell culture is a very demanding test, but currently (with the exception of animal trials) the only means to show the existence of a live virus. . Positive cell culture results indicate the presence of live SARS-CoV in the sample tested.

Negative cell culture results do not exclude SARS.

Antibody detection: Various methods provide a means for the detection of antibodies produced in response to infection with SARS-CoV. Different types of antibodies (IgM and IgG) appear and change in level during the course of infection. They can be undetectable in the early stages of infection. IgG usually remains detectable after resolution of the illness. The following test formats are being developed:

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA): a test which detects a mixture of IgM and IgG antibodies in the serum of SARS patients and reliably yields positive results at around day 21 after the onset of illness.

Immunofluorescence assay (IFA): This requires the use of SARS-CoV-infected cells fixed on a microscope slide; patient antibodies bind to viral antigens and are in turn detected by immunofluorescent-labeled secondary antibodies against human IgG or IgM or both, using an Immunofluorescence microscope. IFA typically yields a positive result after about day 10 after the onset of illness.

Positive antibody test results indicate previous infection with SARS-CoV. Seroconversion from negative to positive or a four-fold rise in the antibody titer from acute to convalescent serum indicates a recent infection. A negative antibody test result later than 21 days after the onset of illness is likely to indicate that no infection with SARS-CoV has taken place.

SARS Treatment

The treatment of coronavirus-associated SARS has been evolving and so far there is no consensus on an optimal regimen. Treatment strategies for SARS were first developed on theoretical bases and from clinical observations and inferences. Prospective randomized controlled treatment trials were understandably lacking during the first epidemic of this novel disease. The mainstream therapeutic interventions for SARS involve broad-spectrum antibiotics and supportive care, as well as antiviral agents and immunomodulatory therapy. Assisted would be instituted in respiratory failure. **Anti-bacterial agents** are routinely prescribed for SARS because its presenting features are non-specific and rapid laboratory tests that can reliably diagnose the SARS-CoV virus in the first few days of infection are not yet available. Appropriate empirical antibiotics are thus necessary to cover against common respiratory pathogens as per national or local treatment guidelines for community-acquired or nosocomial pneumonia respiratory failure.

Various **antiviral agents** were prescribed empirically from the outset of the epidemic and their use was continued despite lack of evidence about their effectiveness

Ribavirin: a nucleoside analog, was widely chosen as an empirical therapy for SARS because of its broad-spectrum antiviral activity against many DNA and RNA viruses. It was commonly used with corticosteroids and has since become the most frequently administered antiviral agent for SARS [5, 10, 14, 22] the use of ribavirin has attracted a lot of criticism due to its unproven efficacy and undue side effects [6]. R toxic concentrations have no direct in vitro activity against SARS-

CoV The prevalence of side effects from ribavirin is dose-related. High doses often result in more adverse effects, such as hemolytic anemia, elevated transaminase levels and bradycardia [11]. However, lower doses of ribavirin did not result in clinically significant adverse effects. Side effects have also been observed more frequently in the elderly. Corticosteroids have been the mainstay of immunomodulatory therapy for SARS. Their timely use often led to early improvement in terms of subsidence of fever, resolution of radiographic infiltrates and better oxygenation, as described in many Chinese and Hong Kong reports [10, 14,]. However, there is much skepticism and controversy about the use of corticosteroids, centering on their effectiveness, adverse immunosuppressive effects and impact on final patient outcomes.

References

- 1- Fouchier R, Kuiken T, Schutten M, et al. Koch's postulates fulfilled for SARS virus. *Nature* 2003; 423: 240.
- 2-CDC. Update: Outbreak of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome - Worldwide, 2003. *MMWR* 2003; 52:241-248.
- 3-Ksiazek TG, Erdman D, Goldsmith CS, et al. A Novel Coronavirus Associated with Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome. *New Eng J Med* 2003, 348:1953-66.
- 4-Drosten C, Preiser W, Günther S, Schmitz H, Doerr HW. Severe acute respiratory syndrome: identification of the etiological agent. *Trends Mol Med* 2003b; 9:325-327.
- 5.Peiris JS, Chu CM, Cheng VC, et al. Clinical progression and viral load in a community outbreak of coronavirus-associated SARS pneumonia: a prospective study. *Lancet* 2003b; 361:1767-72
6. Cyranoski D, Abbott A. Virus detectives seek source of SARS in China's wild animals. *Nature* 2003; 423:467.
7. Enserink M. SARS in China. China's missed chance. *Science* 2003b; 301:294-296.
- 8- Seto WH, Tsang D, Yung R, et al. Effectiveness of precautions against droplets and contact in prevention of nosocomial transmission of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). *Lancet* 2003; 361: 1519–20.
- 9.Cho KO, Hoet AE, Loerch SC, et al. Evaluation of concurrent shedding of bovine coronavirus via the respiratory tract and enteric route in feedlot cattle. *Am J Vet Res* 2001; 62: 1436-41.
- 10.Lee N, Hui D, Wu A, et al. A Major Outbreak of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome in Hong Kong. *N Engl J Med* 2003; 348:1986-94.
- 11..Booth CM, Matukas LM, Tomlinson GA, et al. Clinical features and short-term outcomes of 144 patients with SARS in the greater Toronto area. *JAMA* 2003; 289:28019.
- 12.Chan-Yeung M, Yu WC. Outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome in Hong Kong Special Administrative Region: case report. *BMJ* 2003; 326:850-2

13. Donnelly CA, Ghani AC, Leung GM, et al. Epidemiological determinants of spread of causal agent of severe acute respiratory syndrome in Hong Kong. *Lancet* 2003; 361:1761-6.

14. Tsang KW, Ho PL, Ooi GC, Yee WK, et al. A Cluster of Cases of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome in Hong Kong. *N Engl J Med* 2003, 348:1977-85.

15. Peiris JS, Lai ST, Poon LL, et al. Coronavirus as a possible cause of severe acute respiratory syndrome. *Lancet* 2003a, 361:1319-25. Published online Apr 8, 2003.

16. Fisher DA, Lim TK, Lim YT, Singh KS, Tambyah PA. A typical presentations of SARS. *Lancet* 2003; 361:1740

17. Poutanen SM, Low DE, Henry B, Finkelstein S, et al. Identification of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome in Canada. *N Engl J Med* 2003, 348:1995-2005.

18. Wong R, Wu A, To KF, et al. Hematological manifestations in patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome: retrospective analysis. *BMJ* 2003; 326: 1358-62

19. Wong KT, Antonio GE, Jui D, et al. Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome: Radiographic Appearances and Pattern of Progression in 138 Patients. Published online before print May 20, 2003b.

20. Rainer TH, Cameron PA, Smith D, et al. Evaluation of WHO criteria for identifying patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome out of hospital: prospective observational study. *BMJ* 2003; 326: 1354-8.

21. McIntosh K. Coronaviruses. In: Mandell GL, Bennett JE, Dolin R, eds. *Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases*, 5th ed. Philadelphia: Churchill Livingstone, Inc., 2000.